

Reactions of Aluminium Alkoxides with Acetyl Chloride

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Reactions of primary, secondary, and tertiary alkoxides of aluminium with acetyl chloride have been investigated and the compounds of the following type have been prepared: $\text{Al(OR)}_2\text{Cl}$, $\text{AlCl}_2(\text{OR})$, $0.5\text{CH}_3\text{-COOR}$, $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{CH}_3\text{COOR}$ (where R is methyl, propyl, *n*-, *sec*- or *tert*-butyl). The compounds have been crystallised wherever possible from their respective alcohols. The reaction of aluminium butoxide is found to be very slow. These chloride alkoxides are not stable towards heat and are decomposed during distillation.

Much work has been done on the chloride alkoxides of aluminium¹. Reactions of titanium² and zirconium³ alkoxides with acetyl chloride have been studied in detail. In view of the interesting results obtained with titanium and zirconium, it was considered worthwhile to investigate the similar reactions between aluminium alkoxides (methoxide, propoxide⁴, *n*-, *sec*-, and *tert*-butoxides) and acetyl chloride.

In a detailed study involving acetyl chloride and aluminium propoxide⁴, it was found that no hydrogen chloride was evolved from the possible reaction between propyl alcohol and acetyl chloride, instead quantitative changes were observed which can be represented as :

The reactions were carried out in anhydrous benzene and were found to be strongly exothermic. The compounds were isolated by drying under reduced pressure (about 1 mm) at room temperature (about 25°) to furnish the products which were soluble in organic solvents and in water (with hydrolysis).

The compounds were crystallised, wherever possible, from their respective alcohols, when they showed some tendency of attaching to themselves some alcohol of addition. Unlike the chloride alkoxides of titanium and zirconium, these are not stable to heat and are decomposed to products like alkyl halide, olefines, alcohols, and ethers when attempts are made to distil them even under reduced pressure.

As observed in the reaction of zirconium³ amyloxiide⁴ with acetyl chloride, the reaction of aluminium butoxide⁴ with the latter was found to be very slow. A similar fact was noticed by us in the reaction of aluminium butoxide⁴ with acetyl bromide.

1. Thomae G. m. b. H., *Chemisch-Pharmazeutische Fabrik. Brit.*, May 21, 1958, pp. 795, 222; Funk *et al.*, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1932, 205, 361; Mehrotra and Mehrotra, *ibid.*, 1961.
2. Bradley *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 2773.
3. Bradley *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1952, 4609, 4960.

The interchangeability of radicals in these compounds was shown by refluxing $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 4\text{Pr}^i\text{OH}$ and $\text{AlCl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2$ in anhydrous propanolⁱ in equimolecular proportion, which on cooling gave crystals of dichloride monopropoxideⁱ, according to the equation:

The above study indicates the increasing tendency of the chloride alkoxides in adding the ester or alcohol molecule as the alkoxy group is gradually replaced by the stronger electronegative chloride radical, e.g., $\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ and $\text{AlCl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2$ do not appear to form addition products, whereas $\text{AlCl}_2(\text{OPr}^i)$ and AlCl_3 appear to take 0.5 and 1.5 molecules of ester and 2 and 4 molecules of propanolⁱ of addition under similar conditions.

The chloride alkoxide derivatives of aluminium have been found to be unstable on heating even under reduced pressure and hence these could not be distilled. These differ from the corresponding titanium and zirconium compounds in which case mono- and dichloride alkoxide derivatives can be distilled unchanged.

EXPERIMENTAL

The reactions were carried out in an all-glass apparatus with interchangeable joints and moisture was excluded from all the experiments. A column packed with Rachig rings was used for fractionation.

Aluminium methoxide, propoxideⁱ, butoxides (*n*, *sec.*, and *t*) were prepared as described earlier⁴ and purified by distillation or sublimation under reduced pressure.

Benzene (B.D.H.) was dried over sodium wire and dried finally azeotropically with ethanol over a column. Acetyl chloride (Judex, AnalaR) was carefully fractionated before use. Propanolⁱ was dried over aluminium propoxideⁱ and fractionated. The methyl, butyl (*n*, *sec.*, and *t*) alcohols were dried by refluxing with sodium and fractionated.

Aluminium was estimated as oxinate. Chloride was determined as silver chloride gravimetrically.

Reactions between Aluminium Methoxide and Acetyl Chloride

With Molar Ratio 1:1.—Aluminium methoxide (1.5 g.) was added to acetyl chloride (0.99 g.) causing an exothermic reaction. Benzene (30 ml) was added to it and the mixture refluxed. Excess of solvents was removed by distillation and the residue dried at room temperature (30°/0.01 mm) to afford a white powder (1.5 g.), soluble in water. [Found: Al, 21.3; Cl, 26.8. $\text{AlCl}(\text{OCH}_3)_2$ requires Al, 21.6; Cl, 28.5%].

With Molar Ratio 1:2.—Aluminium methoxide (1.8 g.) was treated with acetyl chloride (2.3 g.) producing a considerable amount of heat. Benzene (20 ml) was added and the mixture refluxed to give a yellow mixture, which was left overnight without any crystallisation. Solvents were distilled and the residue was dried at 25°/0.1 mm to furnish a yellow solid (2.4 g.), soluble in water. [Found: Al, 16.2; Cl, 40.8. $\text{AlCl}_2(\text{OCH}_3) \cdot 0.5\text{-CH}_3\text{COOCH}_3$ requires Al, 16.3; Cl, 42.7%].

With Molar Ratio 1:>3.—Acetyl chloride (3.5 g.) was added to aluminium methoxide (1.2 g.) in benzene (5 ml) causing an exothermic reaction and giving a yellow solution. This mixture was refluxed for half hour. Excess of solvents was removed under reduced

pressure and the residue was dried to give a dark semisolid (2.4 g.). (Found: Al, 10.8; Cl, 40.6; Cl: Al, 2.85. $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 1.5 \text{CH}_3\text{COOCH}_3$ requires Al, 11.0; Cl, 43.5%).

Reactions of Aluminium Propoxideⁱ and Acetyl Chloride

With Molar Ratio 1:1.—Aluminium propoxideⁱ (3.95 g.) was added swiftly to acetyl chloride (1.5 g.) causing evolution of heat. Benzene was added and the clear solution refluxed at 120° for 2 hours. Solvents were removed under reduced pressure to give a white mobile liquid which was dried at 40°/1mm for 2 hours. The paste has a characteristic odour and is soluble in water (3.4 g.). [Found: Al, 14.0; Cl, 19.3. $\text{AlCl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2$ requires Al, 14.9; Cl, 19.6%].

The above paste was dissolved in propanolⁱ and left for cooling. White crystals were obtained which were dried under reduced pressure. [Found: Al, 14.8; Cl, 20.9%]. On attempting to distil the above compound at 250°/0.1 mm, a light residue was left. (Found: Al, 17.7; Cl, 16.1%; Cl: Al, 0.6).

With Molar Ratio 1:2.—Aluminium propoxideⁱ (4.2 g.) was introduced to acetyl chloride (3.26 g.) producing exothermic reaction. After adding benzene (25 ml) the clear solution was refluxed for 2 hours at 120° to furnish a yellowish solution. Solvents were distilled under reduced pressure and the residue was dried at 35-40°/1 mm for 3 hours to give a yellowish crystalline solid having a characteristic smell. It is soluble in water (4.2 g.). [Found: Al, 12.6; Cl, 33.0. $\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 0.5\text{CH}_3\text{COOPr}^i$ requires Al, 12.9; Cl, 34.1%].

The above dichloride was dissolved in minimum quantity of propanolⁱ and allowed to cool overnight. A white compound with a light yellow tinge separated. Mother liquor was rejected and the crystals were dried under reduced pressure for 3 hours. [Found: Al, 10.1; Cl, 25.7. $\text{AlCl}_2(\text{OPr}^i) \cdot 2 \text{Pr}^i\text{OH}$ requires Al, 9.7; Cl, 25.6%].

With Molar Ratio 1:>3.—Aluminium propoxideⁱ (4.2 g.) was added to acetyl chloride (6.5 g.), causing evolution of heat. Benzene (15 ml) was added and the mixture refluxed at 110° to afford a deep red solution. It was dried under reduced pressure to give a red mobile liquid which solidified on keeping. It is soluble in water. (Found: Al, 9.6; Cl, 34.2; Cl: Al, 2.7. $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{CH}_3\text{COOPr}^i$ requires Al, 9.4; Cl, 37.1%).

The above compound was crystallised from dry propanolⁱ. The crystals were dried under reduced pressure at 30° to give a yellow crystalline solid having characteristic smell. It is soluble in water. (Found: Al, 7.4; Cl, 25.7; Cl:Al, 2.7. $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 4\text{Pr}^i\text{OH}$ requires Al, 7.2; Cl, 28.5%).

Reactions of Aluminium Butoxideⁿ and Acetyl Chloride

With Molar Ratio 1:1.—To aluminium butoxideⁿ (3.0 g.) in benzene (15 ml) was added acetyl chloride (0.98 g.). A considerable amount of heat was evolved. The mixture was refluxed and the solvent removed, leaving a residue which was dried under reduced pressure to give a white powder (2.5 g.). It is soluble in water. [Found: Al, 13.4; Cl, 18.0. $\text{AlCl}(\text{OBut}^n)_2$ requires Al, 12.9; Cl, 17.02%].

The above monochloride was dissolved in butanolⁿ and allowed to cool overnight. A little solid separated which was dried under reduced pressure. (Found: Al, 13.6; Cl, 17.6%).

With Molar Ratio 1:2.—Aluminium butoxideⁿ (1.9 g.) was added to acetyl chloride (1.25 g.) causing evolution of heat. Benzene (10 ml) was added and the mixture refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The solvents were removed and the residue was dried to give a yellow paste (1.9 g.), soluble in water, giving a pleasant smell. [Found: Al, 10.8; Cl, 26.5. $\text{AlCl}_2(\text{OBu}^n)$. $0.75\text{CH}_3\text{COOBu}^n$ requires Al, 10.4; Cl, 27.5%].

On attempting to distil, the above compound appeared to decompose giving a light residue. [Found: Al, 19.8; Cl, 20.1%; Cl:Al, 0.76].

With Molar Ratio 1:>3.—Acetyl chloride (4.7 g.) was introduced to a solution of aluminium butoxideⁿ (2.6 g.) in benzene (10 ml) causing an exothermic reaction. The mixture was refluxed for 5 hours to give a red solution. Solvents were distilled at room temperature under reduced pressure and the red paste was dried at $30^\circ/1\text{mm}$ for 2 hours. It has a characteristic smell and is soluble in water (3.8 g.). (Found: Al, 8.3; Cl, 29.4. $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{COOBu}^n$ requires Al, 7.4; Cl, 29.1%).

Reactions of Aluminium Butoxide^{sec} and Acetyl Chloride

With Molar Ratio 1:1.—To acetyl chloride (0.74 g.) were added aluminium butoxide^{sec} (2.2 g.) and benzene (10 ml), producing considerable heat. The mixture was refluxed for half hour to give a colorless solution. After removing solvents the residue was dried under reduced pressure to give a colorless paste, soluble in water (1.9 g.). [Found: Al, 12.9; Cl, 16.2. $\text{AlCl}(\text{OBu}^{\text{sec}})_2$ requires Al, 12.9; Cl, 17.0%].

With Molar Ratio 1:2.—To a solution of aluminium butoxide^{sec} (2.6 g.) in benzene (20 ml) was added acetyl chloride (1.6 g.), causing an exothermic reaction. After refluxing the yellow solution was evaporated under reduced pressure, leaving a yellow paste having a sweet smell. It is soluble in water. [Found: Al, 11.0; Cl, 28.5. $\text{AlCl}_2(\text{OBu}^{\text{sec}})$. $0.75\text{CH}_3\text{COOBu}^{\text{sec}}$ requires Al, 10.4; Cl, 27.5%].

With Molar Ratio 1:>3.—Acetyl chloride (3.4 g.) was admitted to a solution of aluminium butoxide^{sec} (1.4 g.) in benzene (10 ml). On shaking an exothermic reaction was noticed, giving a yellow mixture which was refluxed for 1 hour. The solvents were distilled under reduced pressure and the residue was dried at $30\text{-}40^\circ/1\text{ mm}$ for 3 hours to give a red paste having a characteristic smell. It is soluble in water. (Found: Al, 8.1; Cl, 31.2. $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 1.5\text{CH}_3\text{COOBu}^{\text{sec}}$ requires Al, 8.7; Cl, 34.6%).

Reactions between Aluminium Butoxide^t and Acetyl Chloride

With Molar Ratio 1:>3.—Aluminium butoxide^t (1.0 g.) was dissolved in benzene (25 ml) to give a clear solution. Acetyl chloride (2.6 g.) was introduced to it without producing any noticeable exothermic reaction. The mixture was refluxed for 1 hour. After removing the solvents, the residue was dried at $30^\circ/1\text{ mm}$ to give a white powder (0.8 g.). (Found: Al, 14.6; Cl, 7.6%; Cl:Al, 0.4).

The above analysis shows that not only the reaction is slow, but side decomposition also occurs as the analysis will correspond to a mixed derivative of the type $\text{AlCl}_{3-x}(\text{OH})_x(\text{OBu}^t)_x$. (Calc. Al, 13.7; Cl, 7.2%).

Reaction between $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 4\text{Pr}^i\text{OH}$ and $\text{AlCl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2$ in Equimolecular Ratio in Propanolⁱ

A mixture of $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 4\text{Pr}^i\text{OH}$ (1.0 g.), $\text{AlCl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2$ (0.55 g.), and dry propanolⁱ (20 ml) was refluxed for 20 minutes, resulting in a light yellow solution. This on cooling gave crystals (1.0 g.) which were dried under reduced pressure. [Found: Al, 10.2; Cl, 26.2. $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot (\text{OPr}^i)_2 \cdot 2\text{Pr}^i\text{OH}$ requires Al, 9.7; Cl, 25.6%].

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